

Prioritisation analysis based on biodiversity variables and blue carbon

Deliverable 5.5

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 5.5 overview

This report presents results of preliminary combined prioritisation analysis based on species ranges and where marine sediment organic carbon (OC) storage capacity in the MPA Europe project study area. It uses the updated species range maps (species distribution models, SDMs) developed under the project WP3 (Species and Biogenic habitat Distribution (Principe et al., 2023; OBIS 2024); and the new map of the modelled OC storage capacity in European seas based on the OC content of upper sediment layers and environmental predictors developed under the project WP4 (EURO-CARBON, Lønborg et al., 2025). In this report we compare this map of modelled OC levels (based on environmental predictors) in marine sediments (top 10 cm) with the biodiversity prioritised areas. Through this process, optimal MPA networks covering 10% and 30% of European seas will be identified for biodiversity, blue carbon, and their combined benefits. This spatial information could be used in Marine Spatial Planning, for example by indicating where seabed disturbance should be minimised (e.g., from bottom trawling) to avoid biodiversity loss and remineralisation of seabed organic carbon which may lead to the release of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases from the seabed into the water column.

A next step of the prioritisation analyses will include validated and improved modelled species distributions (SDM) based on partners and expert stakeholders comments; inclusion of the conservation status and extinction risk of biological species, as well as information on non-indigenous species (Principe et al, 2024); the most extreme climate change scenario (SSP5) until 2100; and analyses for EEZ, territorial seas as well as the four regions mapped here. This process will provide the basis for the design of a representative a MPA network.

A final version of the prioritisation map based on all the available biodiversity and blue carbon data will be available for Deliverables D5.6 (Paper on the MPA networks in European Seas based on the prioritisation analyses for biodiversity conservation and blue carbon) and D5.7 (Online atlas for Marine Spatial Planning).

Introduction

European and international initiatives, such as Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (BDS, COM/2020/380 final) and Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF, CBD/COP/15/L25) adopted by the European Union and the Conference of Parties COP15 respectively, called for the protection of at least 30% of each marine habitat globally and at least 30% of all the ocean for worldwide effective marine biodiversity conservation by 2030. The Biodiversity Strategy also requests an additional commitment to strictly protect at least 10% of European seas. The MPA Europe project will identify the optimal places to protect marine biodiversity in an ecologically representative network.

A Marine Protected Area (MPA) network that is representative of the biodiversity in a region can be designed using evidence-based systematic conservation planning that uses decision-support tools such as Zonation (Moilanen et al., 2009). Previous studies both globally (e.g. Zhao et al., 2020) or nationally (e.g., Stephenson et al., 2023) have shown that a data-driven approach can identify the optimal locations for Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in the most cost-effective way while minimizing the area covered, including accounting for predicted shifts in taxa due to climate change. The benefits of effective MPAs include not only the protection of biodiversity, but also the restoration of ecosystems and fisheries, generating benefits for fisheries and ecotourism, and enhancing ecosystem resilience to climate change (Costello, 2024).

In the original proposal we envisaged using maps of benthic habitats, ecosystems and regionalisations in the prioritisation analysis. We have previously used biomes, biogeographic realms, and rugosity (a measure of topographic heterogeneity) in prioritisation analysis at a global scale (Zhao et al. 2020). However, in those cases the spatial resolution was coarse and maps at a global extent were available. Within Europe we do not have sufficient coverage of benthic habitat maps to use in prioritisation because all data layers must be complete to avoid an unbiased analysis. However, because we have species range maps for some 12,000 species based on a suite of biologically relevant environmental variables, the species ranges themselves will account for “biodiversity” at the spatial scale used here of 0.05 degrees.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has defined Blue Carbon as “all biologically driven carbon fluxes and storage in marine systems that are amenable to management”. So far, the Blue Carbon concept has mainly referred to marine sediment organic carbon (OC) that is captured and stored below seagrass meadows, tidal marshes, and mangrove forests, which have a high capacity for OC storage and can all be managed through protection and restoration of lost ecosystems. Protection of their OC stocks may help reduce the risk that the carbon is degraded and released as CO₂ while restoration of lost habitats may increase OC storage and, thereby, contribute to mitigation of climate change. Such management also supports biodiversity, coastal protection, nutrient retention, and other key ecological functions and services (Nellemann et al. 2009, Duarte et al. 2013; Howard et al. 2014; Hilmi et al, 2021). Protecting the seafloor Blue Carbon from disturbances may help reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Howard et al. 2023, Epstein & Roberts 2022). Efficient protection requires knowledge on the variability in sediment OC levels, the factors controlling these, and a scoring system allowing a classification of sediment Blue Carbon levels across sea basins.

Methods

Biodiversity maps

We used maps of the modelled ranges of 12,683 species. The maps were obtained through species distribution models (SDM) developed previously by the project (Principe, 2023) and available online (<https://shiny.obis.org/distmaps>; OBIS, 2024). The raster layers had a spatial resolution of 0.05 degrees (ca 5 km) and were pre-processed with R packages *dpylr*, *terra*, and *arrow* packages in R environment to select the best fitting model and include uncertainty (i.e., using the uncertainty discounting approach described in Moilanen et al., 2006) and to mask the SDMs according to the MPA Europe study area.

Carbon stores map

As next step from D5.4 (Addamo et al., 2025) we used the new map of the modelled organic carbon developed by the MPA Europe project using boosted regression trees (BRT) (Lønborg et al., in prep, M6). The model included different environmental factors, topographic rugosity as well as geomorphic features (Bio-Oracle v3.0, Assis et al., 2024) that might drive the OC levels of marine sediments (Addamo et al., 2024). The model was also validated based on environmental data associated with the update EURO-CARBON dataset that include over 61,000 OC samples across pan-European seas and beyond (Lønborg et al., 2025; Graversen et al., 2025). The raster layer had a spatial resolution of 0.01 degrees (ca 1 km) and was pre-processed with R packages *terra* package in R environment to align the resolution with biodiversity maps and to mask the blue carbon map according to the MPA Europe study area.

Spatial integration analyses

The prioritisation analysis for biodiversity was performed with the software Zonation 5 v1.0 (Moilanen et al., 2022) using the basic default settings and the Core Area Zonation (CAZ1) prioritisation algorithm which iteratively removes the cells that contribute least to the conservation objective.

The prioritisation map for blue carbon was obtained by modelling a map of predicted organic carbon concentrations in sediments throughout the study area and applying the organic carbon index (OCI) (see Graversen et al., 2024) to the final raster layer with a spatial resolution of 0.05 degrees (ca 5 km) with a simpler 3-level score for ease of visualization on maps where: 1-low = 0-0.5% OC; 2-intermediate = 0.5-2 % OC; and 3-high = >2 % OC) (Graversen et al., 2024).

The integration analyses were performed using *terra*, and *ggplot2* packages in R environment to combine and visualize the biodiversity with blue carbon priority areas at spatial scale (R code available at Supplementary Material SM1). The spatial integration analyses included the following different steps and objectives:

1. Running the prioritisation on over 12,000 species using Zonation to identify and rank potential hotspots of biodiversity at pan-European scale;
2. Plotting the performance curves to indicate what proportion of species would be included in the optimal 10% and 30%;
3. Overlapping biodiversity and blue carbon priority maps to identify matching and unique areas of interest, using overall priority maps, optimal 10% and 30% boundaries for biodiversity, and moderate and high organic carbon content for blue carbon;
4. Running the prioritisation on over 12,000 species and map the optimum (top) 10% and 30% for each of the four marine regions (Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean) separately;
5. Plotting and comparing the performance curves between regions and pan-European area to show how much area is needed to achieve the same species coverage;

6. Overlapping biodiversity and blue carbon priority maps, using overall priority maps, optimal 10% and 30% boundaries for biodiversity, and moderate and high organic carbon content for blue carbon to identify matching and unique areas of interest at regional scale.

We found that the Zonation analysis dropped some species in each run, probably due to incompatibilities in the data files. Why this occurs is being researched further but it means the actual number of species is less than the target.

Biodiversity and organic carbon relationship

We overlaid the Zonation overall, 10%, and 30% boundaries on the modelled organic carbon map with the Zonation score per geographic cell to evaluate the presence of a positive, negative or no significant correlation between % OC stores in sediments and biodiversity value. The analysis was performed using *terra* and *ggplot2* packages in R environment to calculate a Pearson linear correlation¹ and spatial focal (or moving window) model².

Prioritisation performance test

To estimate how many species are needed to produce a consistent Zonation output, we compared the prioritisation performance with different samples of species, namely on 500, 3,000 and 5,000 non-overlapping and randomly selected (i.e., not taxonomically or alphabetically or by number of observations or area) species.

Results

Biodiversity

The Zonation analysis prioritised all coastal areas and the continental shelf off the coast of Norway and North Sea, around the Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands, as well as some continental slope near Svalbard and south-west Ireland (Figure 1). Low priority areas were the deep sea between Iceland and Svalbard, and in the eastern Mediterranean. These patterns were evident at both the 10% and 30% areas (Figure 1).

The performance curves showed that the optimal (top) 10% and 30% of the study area would contain ~60% and ~80% of all the species respectively (Figure 2). These curves were similar for the three species samples with 491, 2,919 and 4,110 species (Figures 3-5). Although the spatial prioritisations for these samples may seem similar, they were not identical (Figures 6-9). The number of cells only prioritised by one sample was greater for the smaller samples (Figures 10-11, A1, A2). Thus, with more species analysed the 10% and 30% prioritised areas became more similar.

When we ran Zonation on only each of the four regional sea areas, the relative importance of areas in each region is the same as when all the study area is prioritised (Figures 6-9, A3). The proportions of species protected were about 5% -10% higher at 10% of the area for the smaller seas, but similar for the Atlantic to all of Europe (Figures 6-9).

Biodiversity and Carbon Stores

There was no significant correlation between the priority Zonation attached to a geographic cell and its organic carbon concentration (Figure 12, Figure A4). Thus, when we overlay the top 10% and

¹ Pearson linear correlation is a statistical measure that quantifies the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables. It ranges from -1 to +1, where: -1 indicates a perfect negative linear relationship, +1 indicates a perfect positive linear relationship, and 0 indicates no linear relationship.

² A spatial focal (or moving window) model analyses spatial data by calculating a statistic for a defined neighbourhood around each cell in a raster dataset. This "window" moves across the raster, applying a function (like sum, mean, or max) to the cells within its reach, creating a new raster where each cell represents the result of that calculation for its corresponding neighbourhood (see Hagen-Zanker, A. (2016).

30% prioritised areas on the moderate to high carbon concentrations very few are visible on the map (Figure 13).

Discussion

The areas prioritised are to be expected because most species live in shallow depths, typical along coastal areas and associated with areas of high topographic heterogeneity (“rugosity”) (Costello and Chaudhary 2017, Zhao et al. 2020). Most primary production occurs in shallow depths. Topographic variation may be caused by wave and current conditions, and in turn will influence them, and consequently the seabed substrata. Thus, rocky reefs, canyons, seamounts and other features tend to have greater habitat and species diversity. Large areas of similar seabed conditions, particularly muddy sediments, and especially off the continental shelf, tend to have a lower density and overall species richness (i.e., lower alpha, beta and gamma richness).

Our finding of no correlation between the areas prioritised for biodiversity and areas with higher organic carbon stores is also not surprising. Our previous analyses show that organic carbon concentrations tend to be higher in depositional environments which are wave and current sheltered, the same areas generally lower in species diversity. Together these findings mean that management actions to protect biodiversity and organic carbon need to consider each separately.

Kujala et al. (2018) compared the effect on prioritisation results of including from 10 to 100 terrestrial species. As expected, they found improved results using more species. We find similar results here using between 400 to 12,000 species. However, the 4,919 and 11,626 species prioritisations were similar. We will conduct further analyses to determine when results are identical, indicating sufficient species to be representative of all biodiversity in the study area.

Future work will include re-running the Zonation analyses using the validated and improved SDMs based on partners and stakeholders comments; special consideration of species of conservation importance for conservation and those providing biogenic habitats, and excluding human introduced (invasive) species (Principe et al, 2024); the most extreme climate change scenario (SSP5) until 2100 so as to capture ; and analyses accounting for the sea basins and territorial seas. We will also analyse further samples of species between 5,000 and 12,000 to determine how many species provide the same prioritised areas.

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Figure 1. The prioritisation analysis at pan-European scale (i.e., MPA Europe study area) based on 11,626 species out of set of 12,683 range maps (top; red = high priority, blue = no priority) and the optimal 10% and 30% areas (bottom left and bottom right, respectively; yellow = high priority, blue = low priority).

Figure 2. The performance curve indicating how many species are included in an increasing area.

Figure 3. The prioritisation analysis at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) based on last 491 species out of 500 species (top) and relative performance curve (bottom, as in Figure 2). Red = high priority, blue = no priority.

Figure 4. The prioritisation analysis at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) based on last 2,919 species out of 3,000 species (top) and relative performance curve (bottom, as in Figure 2). Red = high priority, blue = no priority.

Figure 5. The prioritisation analysis at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) based on last 4,110 species out of 5,000 species (top) and relative performance curve (bottom, as in Figure 2). Red = high priority, blue = no priority.

Figure 6. The regional prioritisation analysis in the Baltic Sea based on 11,626 species (top left; yellow = high priority, blue = low priority), overlap with moderate and high organic carbon content $OC > 0.5\%$ (red, top right) and the relative performance curve (bottom, as in Figure 2). The matching areas between biodiversity and OC are shown in red (top right).

Figure 7. As for Figure 6 except for the Black Sea.

Figure 8. As for Figure 6 except for the North-East Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 9. As for Figure 6 except for the Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 10. Combined unique areas of top 10% area of prioritisation layers at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) (top left) based on last 11,626 (red), 4,110 (purple), 2,919 (green) and 491 (blue) species. SD = species distribution maps.

Figure 11. Combined unique areas of top 30% area of prioritisation layers at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) (top left) based on last 11,626 (red), 4,110 (purple), 2,919 (green) and 491 (blue) species. SD = species distribution maps.

Figure 12. The relationships of the Zonation priority score for biodiversity in each geographic cell to the predicted organic carbon concentration (Lønborg et al, in prep) in the same cell in the study area. The blue line is the linear correlation, showing no relationship between the two variables (see also Figure A4).

Figure 13. Spatial overlap of top 10% (top row) and 30% (bottom row) area of biodiversity prioritised areas with the moderate and high organic carbon content (OC > 0.5%). The matching areas between biodiversity and OC are shown in red in the right column.

Appendix

Figure A1. Spatial overlap of top 10% area of prioritisation layers at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) based on last 11,626 (top left), 4,110 (top right), 2,919 (bottom left) and 491 (bottom right) species with relative unique areas.

Figure A2. Spatial overlap of top 30% area of prioritisation layers at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) based on last 11,626 (top left), 4,110 (top right), 2,919 (bottom left) and 491 (bottom right) species with relative unique areas.

Figure A3. Spatial overlap of top 10% area of prioritisation layer at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) (top left) and regional top 10% area of prioritisation layer in the North-East Atlantic (top right) Baltic Sea and Black Sea (middle left and right, respectively), and Mediterranean Sea (bottom) based on last 11,626 species. Yellow = high priority, blue = low priority.

Figure A4. Spatial focal correlation (with a moving window 3x3 cells) at pan-European scale (i.e. MPA Europe study area) between the Zonation priority score for biodiversity in each geographic cell using 11,626 species (see Figure 1) to the predicted organic carbon concentration (Lønborg et al, in prep) in the same cell in the study area. The blue line is the linear correlation, showing no relationship between the two variables. Yellow = positive spatial correlation, blue = negative spatial correlation, showing no clear relationship pattern between the two variables.

